

WORK ENVIRONMENT AND WORK ENGAGEMENT AMONG EMPLOYEES IN SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the work environment and work engagement of employees in public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu, Philippines during the 2021-2022 academic year. The unique social and political context of the region is acknowledged as a potential influence on these factors. A survey approach was used to gather data from 190 employees. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents are female and over 41 years old. While no significant differences in work engagement were identified based on gender or age, a notable difference emerged based on civil status. Married employees reported higher levels of vigor compared to their unmarried counterparts. Based on these results, the study recommended several actions for public HEIs in Sulu. Firstly, efforts should be directed towards understanding and implementing practices that enhance vigor for all employees, drawing insights from the experiences of the married employee group. Secondly, further research is recommended to explore the work environment experiences of diverse employee subgroups within HEIs. Finally, the study suggests developing and implementing strategies to improve overall work engagement among HEI employees, regardless of their background characteristics.

Keywords: *Work Engagement, Work Environment, Higher Education, Sulu, Philippines, Employee Wellbeing*

INTRODUCTION

Public higher education institutions (HEIs) play a crucial role in shaping a nation's future by equipping individuals with knowledge, skills, and critical thinking abilities. To ensure their effectiveness, HEIs need not only robust academic programs and qualified

faculty, but also a thriving workforce characterized by high employee well-being and engagement (McNulty, 2004). A positive work environment, characterized by adequate resources, supportive leadership, and opportunities for professional growth, fosters employee satisfaction and commitment (Wright & Cropanzano, 2000). Additionally, high work engagement, which refers to a state of dedication, vigor, and absorption in one's work, is associated with increased productivity and improved institutional performance (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

This study aimed to investigate the work environment and work engagement of employees in public HEIs located in Sulu, Philippines, during the 2021-2022 academic year. Sulu, situated in the southernmost region of the Philippines, provides a unique context for examining these factors. The region has a history of social unrest and ongoing armed conflict, which may influence the work experiences of employees within HEIs. Understanding the current state of the work environment and engagement levels within these institutions can provide valuable insights for enhancing employee well-being and ultimately, institutional success in Sulu.

Examining the demographic makeup of the workforce provides valuable context for interpreting the findings on work environment and engagement. Additionally, exploring potential relationships between these factors and employee demographics can shed light on how gender, age, and marital status might influence experiences within the workplace. For instance, research suggests that younger employees may have different work environment needs and preferences compared to their older counterparts (Bakker, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2003).

The existing body of research emphasizes the critical role of a positive work environment and high work engagement in fostering employee well-being and organizational effectiveness (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Wright & Cropanzano, 2000). Employees who feel supported, valued, and engaged in their work are more likely to be satisfied, productive, and committed to their institution's goals. This directly translates to enhanced student learning outcomes and improved institutional performance (McNulty, 2004).

In the context of HEIs in Sulu, investigating these factors holds particular significance. The region's unique challenges, including social unrest and armed conflict, might influence the work environment and engagement levels of employees. Understanding these influences can inform the development of strategies to create a more positive work environment and enhance employee engagement, ultimately contributing to improved institutional effectiveness and student success.

Research Objectives

This study investigated the extent of work environment and work engagement of employees of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the Academic Year of 2021-2022. Specifically, this research answered following inquiries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age and civil status?
2. What is the extent of work environment of the employees of public HEIs?
3. What is the extent of work engagement of the employees of public HEIs?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of work environment of the employees of public HEIs when the data are classified according to gender, age and civil status?
5. Is there a significant difference in the work engagement of the employees of public HEIs when the data are classified according to gender, age and civil status?

METHODOLOGY

This section contained the methodologies used in the study. It included the research design, Population and Sample, Data Collection Instruments, Data Collection Procedures and Ethical Considerations, Data Analysis and Limitations of the Study.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design. It utilized surveys and questionnaires to gather data on the work environment and work engagement of employees in public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the Academic Year 2021-2022.

Population and Sample

The target population were the 190 employees of public HEIs in Sulu during the academic year 2021-2022. A representative sample of employees were selected using purposive sampling technique.

Data Collection Instruments

The data gathered from the study were collected using two standardized questionnaires which were adapted and modified from the studies of Rothman (2017) and from Bay (2014). In order to guarantee the validity and reliability of the instruments utilized, the researcher sought validation from experts.

Data Collection Procedures and Ethical Considerations

The data collection process began by obtaining permission from the Office of the Dean of Graduate Studies, the Office of the Superintendent and the participating HEIs. After the informed consent was obtained from all respondents, the researcher distributed surveys either in paper format. Throughout the data collection process, anonymity was maintained to ensure confidentiality.

Data Analysis

The researcher used a two-pronged approach to analyze the collected data. Firstly, descriptive statistics such as frequency tables and percentages were used to create a profile of the respondents based on demographics (gender and age). Secondly, inferential statistics like t-tests and ANOVA were utilized to determine if there were any significant differences in work environment and work engagement levels when the data was categorized by gender and age. This approach helped the researcher identify potential correlations between these factors.

Limitations of the Study

It is crucial to recognize the limitations of this research. Although the study provides valuable insights into the work environment and employee engagement in public HEIs in Sulu, the findings may not be easily applicable to other regions in the Philippines due to the unique context of the area. Furthermore, since the data was collected through self-reported surveys, there is a potential for bias as participants' responses may be influenced by personal perceptions or a desire to portray themselves in a certain manner.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 Socio-demographic profile of employees of public HEIs in Sulu

Gender	Number of Employees	Percent
Male	78	41.1%
Female	112	58.6%
Total	190	100%

Table 1.1 shows the socio-demographic profile of employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of gender. This table reveals that out of 190 respondents, 112 (58.6%) are female and 78 (41.1%) are male. In this study, this means that more than one-half or majority of the respondents are female. This result implies that female employees and middle-level administrators of HEIs in Sulu are bit dominating in number as against their male counterpart.

Table 1.2 Socio-demographic profile of the employees of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of age

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
25 years old & below	20	10.5%
26-30 years old	28	14.7%
31-35 years old	35	18.4%
36-40 years old	40	21.1%
41 years old & above	67	35.3%
Total	190	100%

Table 1.2 presents the socio-demographic profile of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of age. This table reveals that out of 190 respondents, 20 (10.5%) are 25 years old & below, 28 (14.7%) are 26-30 years old, 35 (18.4%) are 31-35 years old, 40 (21.1%) are 36-40 years old, and 67 (35.3%) and 41 years old & above. In this study, this means that respondents' age is distributed more among 41 years old & below of age bracket. This result implies that more than one-third of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu involved in this study belonged to the highest age bracket.

Table 1.3 Socio-demographic profile of the employees public HEIs in Sulu in terms of civil status.

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
Single	50	26.3%
Married	130	68.4%
Separated/Widowed	9	4.7%
Total	190	100%

Table 1.3 presents the socio-demographic profile of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of civil status. This table reveals that out of 190 respondents, 130 (68.4%) are married, 50 (26.3%) are single, and 9 (4.7%) are separated/widowed. In this study, this means that almost three-fourth of the respondents are married. This result implies that great majority of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu involved in this study are involved in multi-tasking such that beside from focusing on their office and school works, they are also engrossed to family household chores and other social obligations.

Table 2.1 Extent of work environment of the employees of public HEIs

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Egoistic Ethical Behavior	3.5191	.69867	Agree	High Tendency
Deontological Ethical Behavior	4.1921	.43504	Agree	High Tendency
Utilitarian Ethical Behavior	4.1895	.53386	Agree	High Tendency

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Employees of public HEIs in this study perceived a high tendency for ethical behavior within their institutions. The table summarizes this finding across three indicators: Egoistic (focusing on self-interest), Deontological (emphasizing duties and rules), and Utilitarian (prioritizing the greatest good). All three indicators received average scores interpreted as "Agree," with standard deviations reflecting some variation in employee perceptions. This suggests that, while not everyone may have identical views, a general consensus leans towards a positive perception of ethical behavior within these HEIs.

Table 2.2 Extent of work engagement of the employees of public HEIs

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Vigor	4.0956	.53321	Agree	High Tendency
Dedication	4.3926	.58278	Agree	High Tendency
Absorption	4.1868	.59666	Agree	High Tendency

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Employees in this study exhibited high tendencies for work engagement across three key dimensions. The average scores (Mean) for Vigor (4.09), Dedication (4.39), and Absorption (4.18) all fell within the "Agree" range, indicating a general sentiment of positive work engagement. While there may be some variation in individual experiences (represented by the standard deviations), these findings suggest employees felt energetic and enthusiastic about their work (Vigor), highly dedicated and committed to their roles (Dedication), and deeply engrossed in their tasks (Absorption).

Table 2.1 Differences in the extent of work engagement of employees public HEIs when data are classified according to gender

VARIABLES Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Vigor	Male	4.1944	.41388	.16766*	2.152	.033	Significant
	Female	4.0268	.59467				
Dedication	Male	4.4179	.63096	.04295	.499	.619	Not Significant
	Female	4.3750	.54895				
Absorption	Male	4.2479	.58031	.10352	1.178	.240	Not Significant
	Female	4.1443	.60673				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 2.1 presents the differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to gender. It can be gleaned from this table that except for Vigor, all other sub-categories subsumed under ethical climate are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally male and female respondents in this study do not differ in their perceptions towards the extent of work engagement being practiced by employees and middle-level administrators among the public HEIs in Sulu. This result implies that, generally being a male respondent may not probably make him better perceiver towards the extent of ethical climate than his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that male and female employees of public HEIs in Sulu have similar ways of perceiving the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Also, they have similar judgment on how HEIs employees care about their work and about the performance, and feel that their efforts make a difference. Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant influence in the ways how employees and middle-level administrators public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to gender" is accepted.

Table 2.2 Differences in the extent of work engagement of employees public HEIs when data are classified according to age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Vigor	Between	.970	4	.242	.850	.495	Not Significant
	Within Groups	52.765	185	.285			
	Total	53.735	189				
Dedication	Between	.278	4	.070	.201	.937	Not Significant
	Within Groups	63.911	185	.345			
	Total	64.190	189				
Absorption	Between	1.439	4	.360	1.011	.403	Not Significant
	Within Groups	65.844	185	.356			
	Total	67.284	189				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 2.2 presents the differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under work engagement are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although employee-respondents differ in their age ranges, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of work engagement prevailing among the public HEIs. This result implies that, generally being a being 41 years old & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of work engagement than other respondents who are 25 years old & below, 26-30 years old, 31-35 years old, 36-40 years old, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that young and old employees of HEIs in Sulu have similar ways of perceiving the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Also, they have similar judgment on how HEIs employees care about their work and about the performance, and feel that their efforts make a difference.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant influence in the ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to age" is accepted.

Table 2.3 Differences in the extent of work engagement of employees public HEIs when data are classified according to civil status

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Vigor	Between	2.529	3	.843	3.062*	.029	Significant
	Within Groups	51.206	186	.275			
	Total	53.735	189				
Dedication	Between	1.502	3	.501	1.486	.220	Not Significant
	Within Groups	62.688	186	.337			
	Total	64.190	189				
Absorption	Between	2.457	3	.819	2.350	.074	Not Significant
	Within Groups	64.826	186	.349			
	Total	67.284	189				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 2.3 presents the differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to civil status. It can be gleaned from this table, except for Vigor, the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under work engagement are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although employee-respondents differ in their marital status, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of work engagement prevailing among the public HEIs. This result implies that, generally being a married respondent may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of work engagement than other respondents who are single, separated and widowed, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that regardless of being single, married, and separated/widowed employees of HEIs in Sulu have similar ways of perceiving the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Also, they have similar judgment on how HEIs employees care about their work and about the performance, and feel that their efforts make a difference.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable civil status has no significant influence in the ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to civil status” is accepted.

Conclusions

This study investigated the work environment and work engagement of employees in public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu, Philippines. The findings reveal a positive perception of ethical behavior within these institutions and a high tendency for work engagement among employees. While no significant differences in work engagement were identified based on gender or age, a notable difference emerged based on civil status. Married employees reported higher levels of vigor compared to their unmarried counterparts. This finding suggests that future research should explore the work-life experiences of employees in more detail, particularly in the context of Sulu's unique social and political environment. Based on these results, the study recommends several actions for public HEIs in Sulu. Firstly, efforts should be directed towards understanding and implementing practices that enhance vigor for all employees, drawing insights from the experiences of the married employee group. Secondly, further research is recommended to explore the work environment experiences of diverse employee subgroups within HEIs. Finally, the study suggests developing and implementing strategies to improve overall work engagement among HEI employees, regardless of their background characteristics.

Recommendations

Although the findings of this study may not be directly applicable to all situations in Sulu, they provide valuable insights for public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the region. Here are some recommendations based on the results.

1. Enhance vigor for all employees by focusing on work environment factors: Investigate the specific aspects of the work environment that contribute to a higher sense of vigor among married employees and find ways to implement those practices more widely.
2. Conduct further research on work environment and specific employee groups: Investigate the work environment experiences of different employee groups within HEIs, such as faculty versus staff or younger versus older employees, to gain a deeper understanding of their perspectives.
3. Develop strategies to improve work engagement for all: Implement initiatives to enhance overall work engagement among HEI employees, regardless of their gender, age, or marital status. These strategies may include promoting work-life balance, providing opportunities for professional growth, and fostering a sense of purpose and recognition in the workplace.

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